

The Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion

also known as “jarthoṣṭī dharm samajavā māṭe ilme kṣnumnī cāvī (Gujarati)”

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Zoroastrianism, Parsis (India), Text, Cosmology, Cosmogony, Ilm-e-Khshnoom

‘The key of Ilme Kṣnum to understand the Zoroastrian religion’ is the first book authored by Behramshah Naoroji Shroff (1858-1927), a Parsi gentleman from Surat, Gujarat (India). In 1906, Shroff made known Ilm-e-Khshnoom, an esoteric interpretation of Zoroastrianism, among the Parsis and spread its beliefs until his death. It is believed that he acquired such esoteric knowledge over three years, while he was staying with a community of Zoroastrian sages secluded in a village situated on Mount Damavand, in Iran. Ilm-e-Khshnoom offers a reconciliation between Persianate and Western systems of esoteric knowledge. ‘The Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion’ is the first book published by Shroff and represents his only publication where the beliefs of Ilm-e-Khshnoom are systematically presented as a set of natural laws. In this regard, it is a fundamental text to further our understanding of Ilm-e-Khshnoom from a historical, cultural, sociological, and linguistic point of view. The following publications of Shroff, instead, focus on specific aspects of the Zoroastrian liturgy or of the Parsi life. Being the first publication of Shroff as well as the first book on the subject of Ilm-e-Khshnoom, ‘The Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion’ inaugurates the religious literature consisting of hundreds of books and articles, mainly composed in Gujarati. This knowledge production still continues nowadays, though English has become the main language used for publications. Besides offering a thorough overview of the system of beliefs of Ilm-e-Khshnoom, one of the key features of this book is the presence of a large number of technical terms (also known in Gujarati as logato) whose genealogical study sheds light on the hermeneutical choices adopted by Shroff. Further, the dedication note and the foreword contain important elements that allow to ascribe the story of the initiation of Shroff and the relation with his masters to some narrative elements of the nationalist discourse of the 19th and 20th centuries-Iran. The textual analysis of this book, in effect, uncovers the cultural entanglements between the Persianate world, the Western sphere of influence, and India. The Parsis play a critical role in these entanglements, furthering connections and favouring cultural transfers; in particular, transculturation. Ilm-e-Khshnoom and ‘The Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion’, in this regard, are the result of such entanglements and activities of transculturation between the Persianate, the West, and India.

Date Range: 1911 CE - 2022 CE

Region: Persianate World

Region tags: Persianate World

Region sharing Persian culture, language, and material culture (7th to 19th centuries CE)

Status of Readership:

✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Shroff, B. N. 1911. jarthoštī dharm samajavā māṭe ilme kṣnumnī cāvī ('The key of Ilme Kṣnum to understand the Zoroastrian religion') - Bird's eye-view of Ilm-i-Khshnum. Surat: Sām̄j Vartamān.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.frashogard.com/ilm-e-khshnoom-skydrive/books-by-ustad-saheb/>

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.frashogard.com/ilm-e-khshnoom-skydrive/>

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

- Printed with moveable type

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. Jarthoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sām̄j Vartamān, 1911.

Number of sheets

- Bound

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. Jarthoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sām̄j Vartamān, 1911.

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

- Paper

Specify type of paper

- Specify: Uncoated paper stocks

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

- Physical preparation

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. Jarthoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī ('the Key of

Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sāṃj Vartamān, 1911.

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Corrections

Notes: The text was produced by means of note-taking of the personal assistant of the author, who did not write it directly. Therefore, inconsistencies and misspellings abound in the text.

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

↳ Tomb

– No

↳ Cemetery

– No

↳ Temple

– Yes

Notes: Some copies are available at the Dhana Patel Boyce Agiary in Mumbai, India. Other copies are available in private libraries

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

↳ Shrine

– No

↳ Altar

– No

↳ Devotional marker

– No

↳ Cenotaph

– No

- ↳ Church
 - No
- ↳ Mosque
 - No
- ↳ Synagogue
 - No
- ↳ Triumphal Arch
 - No
- ↳ Monument
 - No
- ↳ Mass Gathering Point
 - No
- ↳ Cave(s)
 - No
- ↳ Hilltops
 - No
- ↳ Other natural sanctuaries
 - No
- ↳ Boundary markers or lines
 - No
- ↳ Domestic contexts
 - Yes

Notes: Parsi devotees of Behramshah Naoroji Shroff may hold old copies at home

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kşnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

↳ Library/archive

– Yes

Notes: A copy is stored in the First Dastoor Meherjirana Library in Navsari, Gujarat (India)

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

↳ Specify

– Specify: None

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Notes: It was funded by the Parsi philanthropist Bahmanji Dinsha Petit (1859-1915).

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naorji. Jarthoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sāṃj Vartamān, 1911.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Notes: It is rather an interpretation of religious scriptures and rituals.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– No

↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– No

↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?

– Yes

Notes: It is composed in Parsi Gujarati, however many technical terms (Guj. logato) unknown by Parsis are introduced. These newly introduced terms proceeds from Avestan, Middle Persian, Persian and Arabic, or a combination of them.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kşnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

↳ Possess its own distinct written language?

– No

↳ If known: which authority (authorities) describe(s) the language as sacred?

[Select all that apply]

– Other [specify]: The general language is not considered as sacred, while the technical terms are believed to have been transmitted to the author by a secluded group of Zoroastrian sages who live in Iran.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kşnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?

– No

↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support religious study of text?

– Yes

Notes: Numerous compositions in Gujarati and English aiming at interpreting the text have been produced during the 20th and 21st centuries.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kşnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

Reference: Boyce, Mary. Textual Sources for the Study of Zoroastrianism. University of Chicago Press, 1990.

https://books.google.com/books/about/Textual_Sources_for_the_Study_of_Zoroast.html?hl=&id=ZPlmnX7AgMEC.

↳ Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?

– Yes

Notes: Although much of the knowledge associated with the text have been later codified, there are still oral narrations about the author and his experience with the secluded Zoroastrian sages of Iran.

Reference: Tavaría, Phiroz N.. A Manual of 'khshnoom'. The Zoroastrian Occult Knowledge. Bombay: Parsee Vegetarian & Temperance Society and Zoroastrian Radih Society, 1971.

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Total audience: 100000

Notes: This refers to the global Parsi diaspora.

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (estimated population, numerical)

– Number: 50000

Notes: This refers to the estimated number of total Parsis in India.

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

– smallest audience: 300

Notes: This is the estimated number of contemporary followers of IIm-e-Khshnoom.

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

– largest audience: 70000

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size

– Specify: Marginalisation of textual production associated with IIm-e-Khshnoom; demographic decline of Parsis.

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (% of sample region population, numerical)

– Number: 0.1

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

– smallest audience: 0.0001

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

– largest audience: 100

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size

– Specify: Secularisation, decline of priestly authority, progressive process of individualisation.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kşnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

↳ Nature of audience

[select all that apply]

– Small religious group (one of many small religious groups in sample region)

Notes: The audience refers to followers of the Zoroastrian religion.

↳ Can scholarly and emic notions of the audience differ?

– No

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

Notes: It is to be noted that proselytization happens only within the ethnoreligious community.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kşnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

– No

↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?

– No

↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?

– No

↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?

– Yes

↳ Does proselytization take place regardless of the fact that the text is silent on the matter?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Notes: The Zoroastrian community of India is characterised by a hermeneutical plurality, meaning that there are several groups competing with each other when it comes to interpretation of religion.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kšnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: It belongs to the (Zoroastrian) Ilme Kšnum Book Series.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kşnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– Yes

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kşnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

↳ How is the authority established?

– Yes

Notes: The authority is established on epistemic variables. The author of this text is believed to have spent three years in seclusion in Iran, where he was initiated into an esoteric interpretation of Zoroastrianism.

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– Yes

Notes: This text is not considered as a 'sacred' canon as it does not represent a revelatory content; it is rather a discursive exposition of an esoteric interpretation of Zoroastrianism produced by an individual who had first-hand experience about it. In this context, interpretive and explanatory notes by later authors have been published.

↳ Have major debates shifted the sense of the place of the text with respect to the larger canon?

– No

Notes: It has not changed for the Parsis who believe in this interpretation; however, this text is contested within the community.

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Notes: It belongs to the religious literature on Ilm-e-Khshnoom composed from 1911 onwards.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kşnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

Notes: This literature includes prescriptive texts where guidance about the Zoroastrian liturgy and the adherence to puriy laws are given.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: It's part of the hermeneutical tradition of modern Parsis.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Index

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. Jarthoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sām̄j Vartamān, 1911.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

↳ Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– Yes

Notes: In the foreword, the author writes a dedication note to his master, Sraoṣāvarej Marjbān, a mythical Iranian incorporeal sage who is believed to live in seclusion in Iran.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. Jarthoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sām̄j Vartamān, 1911.

↳ Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– No

↳ How is the lineage established?

– Student-Teacher Relationship

Notes: The author of the text claims to have been initiated by Sraoṣāvarej Marjbān, his master, in Iran during a period of three years

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism.

History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. Jarthoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sām̄j Vartamān, 1911.

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– Yes

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. Jarthoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sām̄j Vartamān, 1911.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

↳ What is the arrangement of the calendar? [Select all that apply]

– Solar?

Notes: Shroff emphasises the importance of following the Fasli calendar, which at the time of the publication of the text was not yet popular in India. He has been one of those who led the introduction of this calendar among the Parsis. By now, there are a few Parsis who follow this calendar and two fire temples whose ceremonial activities follow the Fasli liturgy.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. Jarthoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sām̄j Vartamān, 1911.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

Reference: Panaino, Antonio, Reza Abdollahy, and Daniel Balland. "CALENDARS". Encyclopædia Iranica 4, no. -1 (December 15, 1990). <https://iranicaonline.org/articles/calendars>.

↳ Does the calendar specifically dictate acceptable times for certain activities?

– Yes

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. Jarthoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sām̄j Vartamān, 1911.

↳ Planting?

– No

↳ Water management? (such as opening or closing dams/dykes)

– No

↳ Harvest?

– No

Notes: The Fasli calendar is a harvest-based system that was used across South Asia. However, the author does not mention a norms associated with harvesting in relation to the calendar.

↳ Naming ceremonies (for toddlers)?

– No

↳ "First haircuts" (pre-teen)

– No

↳ Ceremonies marking puberty/entry into adulthood?

– No

↳ Marriage?

– No

↳ House construction (often a metaphor for marriage)?

– No

↳ Divorce?

– No

↳ Warfare?

– No

↳ Funerary services?

– Yes

Notes: The calendar indicates acceptable times for the performance of the fravardīgān, which is the period at the end of the religious year when the dead are commemorated through specific rituals. While this kind of ceremonies is performed by all Zoroastrians, other calendars which are more popular prescribe different times/methods.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. *Jarhoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī* ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat):

Sām̄j Vartamān, 1911.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

↳ Trade/commerce?

– No

↳ Festivals?

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals?

–Specify: six times a year

Notes: The Fasli calendar indicates times for the performance of Gahambars, which are seasonal festivals.

Reference: Rose, Jenny. "Festivals and the Calendar". In *The Wiley Blackwell Companion to Zoroastrianism*, edited by Michael Stausberg and Yuhan Vevaina Sohrab-Dinshaw. Chichester: John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, 2015.

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s)?

–Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Only Parsis following the Fasli calendar participate in Gambahars associated with this calendar. Other calendars prescribe the performance of Gambahars in other times of the year.

↳ On average, how many participants are gathered at festivals?

–number: 100

Notes: This is based on ethnographic fieldwork.

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s)?

– Yes

Notes: This is based on ethnographic fieldwork.

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population?

– No

↳ Pilgramages?

– No

↳ Feasting?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: By employing and re-interpreting Avestan terms, Shroff explains that humans are formed by nine components divided in three layers. These are 'earthly body' (tanu), 'vital organs' (gaethā), 'subtle counterpart of the physical body' (ajam̄d), 'life-energy' (uštān), 'subtle body' (keherp), 'abode of desires' (tevišī), 'radiance of the light of spiritual knowledge' (baodaṃghah) and 'spirit' (phravaši).

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. *Jarhoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī* ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sāṃj Vartamān, 1911.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

Notes: Spirit-Mind is considered to belong to the subtle world; in particular, the component baodaṃghah is associated with the mind from a subtle point of view inasmuch as the author translates this Avestan term as 'radiance of the light of spiritual knowledge'.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. *Jarhoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī* ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sāṃj Vartamān, 1911.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– Yes

Notes: It is conceived as belonging to the subtle world, hence non-physical.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. *Jarhoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī* ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sāṃj Vartamān, 1911.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– Yes

Notes: By employing and re-interpreting Avestan terms, Shroff explains that humans are

formed by nine components divided in three layers. These are 'earthly body' (tanu), 'vital organs' (gaethā), 'subtle counterpart of the physical body' (ajaṃd), 'life-energy' (uštān), 'subtle body' (keherp), 'abode of desires' (tevīšī), 'radiance of the light of spiritual knowledge' (baodaṃghah) and 'spirit' (phravašī).

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. Jarthoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sāṃj Vartamān, 1911.

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– Yes

Notes: In particular, the author describes a state of trance in which teachers transmit knowledge in the form of images to their disciples.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. Jarthoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sāṃj Vartamān, 1911.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

↳ Are there generally positive or negative associations with aggregates?

– Generally positive

↳ If associations with mental aggregates are neither positive or negative, are there other important details to know?

– Specify: The text only refers to a particular mental state used by sages as a method to teach.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. Jarthoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sāṃj Vartamān, 1911.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– No

Notes: The largest part of followers of Ilm-e-Khshnoom do not engage much with primary textual sources; they rather join public event and lectures to get general knowledge about Ilm-e-Khshnoom. Besides these occasions, the debate mind-body is not common among the followers of Ilm-e-Khshnoom.

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– No

Notes: There is a general understanding among Parsis about the division between soul/spirit and body. Ethnographic research shows that the differentiation between soul and spirit is not evident among Parsis, even if textual sources indicate a clear distinction between these two components.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. *Jarhoṣṭī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī* ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sām̄j Vartamān, 1911.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

Notes: According to Ilme Kṣnum, individuals consist of nine components grouped in three layers. The first layer is that of the physical body, which is composed by the 'earthly body' (tanu), the 'vital organs' (gaethā) and the 'subtle counterpart of the physical body' (ajam̄d). The second layer is formed by the 'life-energy' (uṣtān), the 'subtle body' (keherp) and the 'abode of desires' (tevīṣī). The last layer consists of the 'soul' (urvān), the 'radiance of the light of spiritual knowledge' (baodaṃghah) and the 'spirit' (phravaṣī).

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. *Jarhoṣṭī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī* ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sām̄j Vartamān, 1911.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– No

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– No

Notes: It is difficult to identify mainstream vs minority positions as the community enjoy a wide plurality of views; though Ilm-e-Khshnoom counts on a small number of adherents, making it a minority group. In the light of such pluralism, ancient textual sources (i.e. Avesta) have been scrutinised and have produced different interpretations about the composition of humans in terms spirit-matter dualism.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. *Jarhoṣṭī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī* ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sām̄j Vartamān, 1911.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. *Jarhoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī* ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sām̄j Vartamān, 1911.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– Yes

Notes: Hastī 'existence' is the spiritual realm where, according to the text, souls go after death.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. *Jarhoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī* ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sām̄j Vartamān, 1911.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– No

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– No

Notes: It is rather defined as subtle dimension.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. *Jarhoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī* ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sām̄j Vartamān, 1911.

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

Notes: After death, souls go into the process of 'spiritual bargaining' (kharīd pharokht) which lasts 57 years. Depending on the outcome, they will be proceed the journey in the spiritual realm or reincarnate.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. *Jarhoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī* ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sām̄j Vartamān, 1911.

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– Yes

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. *Jarhoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī* ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sāṃj Vartamān, 1911.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

↳ In human form?

– Yes

Notes: After death, humans who still need to go through spiritual development may reincarnate into a human body.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. *Jarhoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī* ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sāṃj Vartamān, 1911.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

↳ In animal/plant form?

– No

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s)?

– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage, etc.)?

– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma)?

– Yes

Notes: The concept of reincarnation follows the 'Law of Universal Compensation and Adjustment' (*kešāś*). In the text, it is described as a mechanism of nature that evaluates the deeds that a soul accomplishes across its various incarnations.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. *Jarhoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī* ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sāṃj Vartamān, 1911.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world?

– No

↳ In textual exegesis among practitioners are there debates about reincarnation?

– No

Notes: Among Zoroastrians following Ilm-e-Khshnoom there is no doubt about reincarnation. However, it is worth noting that a part of the Parsi population do not believe in reincarnation and opt for an interpretation of scriptures as suggested by philologists.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. *Jarhoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī* ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sām̄j Vartamān, 1911.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– Yes

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. *Jarhoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī* ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sām̄j Vartamān, 1911.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

↳ Cremation?

– No

↳ Mummification?

– No

↳ Interment?

– No

↳ Cannibalism?

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying)?

– Yes

Notes: Corpses are initially exposed in circular structures known as dakhma 'tower of silence' where they are subject to air and sun drying.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism.

History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Restless Souls: The Impact of COVID-19 on the Funerary Ceremonies of the Parsis in Mumbai". *Coronasur: Religion and COVID-19*, November 12, 2020. <https://ari.nus.edu.sg/20331-63/>.

↳ Feeding to animals?

– Yes

Notes: Historically, the corpses exposed in towers of silence were subject to excarnation operated by vultures. With the current near-extinction of these animals, crows nowadays usually excarnate the corpses or part of them.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kşnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Restless Souls: The Impact of COVID-19 on the Funerary Ceremonies of the Parsis in Mumbai". *Coronasur: Religion and COVID-19*, November 12, 2020. <https://ari.nus.edu.sg/20331-63/>.

↳ Secondary burial?

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse?

– No

↳ Are there specific designations for parts of corpses?

– No

↳ Could parts of corpses become transformed into partial bodily relics?

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text describes some practices to be performed after the death of an individual to accompany the journey of the spiritual components into the afterlife.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. *Jarhoṣṭī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī* ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sāṃj Vartamān, 1911.

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– No

Notes: They take place in the precinct of the tower of silence.

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– No

Notes: Practices take place for accompanying the soul of the deceased in the journey in the afterlife.

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. *Jarhoṣṭī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī* ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sāṃj Vartamān, 1911.

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. *Jarhoṣṭī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī* ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sāṃj Vartamān, 1911.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– No

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. *Jarhoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī* ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sāṃj Vartamān, 1911.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

– Specify: The supreme high god is unfathomable, hence no qualities can be assigned to describe it.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. *Jarhoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī* ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sāṃj Vartamān, 1911.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. *Jarhoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī* ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sāṃj Vartamān, 1911.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– No

Notes: The capacity of 'seeing' is not proper to indicate the knowledge that the high god has of everything created.

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– No

Notes: The capacity of 'seeing' is not proper to indicate the knowledge that the high god has of everything created.

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– No

Notes: The capacity of 'seeing' is not proper to indicate the knowledge that the high god has of everything created.

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: The supreme god is the creator of the world, therefore has full knowledge of it.

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Can reward

– Yes

Notes: The natural laws set by the supreme deity regulate the process of reward and punishment in the afterlife.

↳ Can punish

– Yes

Notes: The natural laws set by the supreme deity regulate the process of reward and punishment in the afterlife.

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Notes: The supreme deity has indirect and direct causal efficacy in the world.

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– No

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– No

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– No

↳ Can be hurt?

– No

↳ Can be tricked?

– No

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– Yes

Notes: The worship of a number of deities as well as natural elements are included in the liturgy as described by Ilm-e-Khshnoom.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature
– Specify: No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living
– No

Notes: No in a direct way, other divine entities can communicate with the living.

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?
– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Notes: One exception is the fravardigan celebration, when a set of rituals take place to commemorate the deads and, according to the text, their spirits come to the earth.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. *Jarhoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī* ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sām̄j Vartamān, 1911.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. *Jarhoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī* ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sām̄j Vartamān, 1911.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen
– No

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt
– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world
– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
– Yes

Notes: Each divine entity other than the supreme god has a specific responsibility in the physical world.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
– Yes

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)
– Yes

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
– Yes

↳ Have other knowledge of this world
– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?
– No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: The specific qualities depend on the specific area of attributions/scope assigned to the supernatural being.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Notes: Rather than a pantheon of supernatural beings, the text refers to some divine entities which cover specific functions in the existence.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. *Jarhoṣṭī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī* ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sām̄j Vartamān, 1911.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– Yes

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. *Jarhoṣṭī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī* ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sām̄j Vartamān, 1911.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be seen?

– Yes

Notes: These beings decide themselves who to be seen from.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be felt?

– Yes

Notes: These beings can decide themselves who to be felt from.

↳ Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living according to this text?

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– Yes

Notes: Only to selected individuals who have been chosen and invited to the homeplace of the beings, in Mount Damavand (Iran).

↳ In dreams?

– No

↳ In trance possession?

– Yes

Notes: According to the text, these beings practise sejhda, intended as a state of trance where teachings can be transmitted 'visually' to the mind of individuals.

↳ Through divination practices?

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

–Other [specify]: No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. *Jarhoṣṭī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī* ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sāṃj Vartamān, 1911.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– No

Notes: It is unspecified.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. *Jarhoṣṭī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī* ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sāṃj Vartamān, 1911.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

↳ At specified time in future

– No

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– Yes

Notes: The text describes cyclical time periods without specifying which one is the current one. However, signs of decline (i.e. modernisation) indicate that eschaton is in the near future.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. Jarthoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sāṃj Vartamān, 1911.

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– No

↳ At some other time [specify]

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end

– Yes

Notes: Following the tenets of their religion in the most strict possible way. Such tenets include purity laws, societal norms, and ritual performance.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. Jarthoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sāṃj Vartamān, 1911.

↳ Divine judgment event

– No

↳ Restoration of the world

– No

Notes: There is no a single event of restoration of the world inasmuch as the view of time is cyclical.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. Jarthoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sāṃj Vartamān, 1911.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle

– Yes

Notes: In the cyclical view of time, periods of 'restoration' follow periods of 'destruction' of the world.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. *Jarhoṣṭī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī* ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sām̄j Vartamān, 1911.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

↳ Establishment of new political system

– No

↳ Establishment of new religious system

– No

↳ Other form of eschatology?

– Specify: No

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?

– No

Notes: It is not specified in the text, though other related texts describe that a small group of Zoroastrians will escape and settled in the North Pole until a new time cycle starts.

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Notes: There are numerous comments about the importance of following the religious observances, though details about specific social norms are absent.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. *Jarhoṣṭī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī* ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sām̄j Vartamān, 1911.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Notes: There is a rather unified morality between social and religious life.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. *Jarhoṣṭī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī* ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sām̄j Vartamān, 1911.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Notes: Even if virtues are not directly cited, the text encourages what could be defined as a 'pious' life, intended as a life dedicated to the performance of religious observances.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. *Jarhoṣṭī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī* ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sām̄j Vartamān, 1911.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: It exerts to follow strictly religious observances.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naorji. Jarthoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sām̃j Vartamān, 1911.

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Notes: When referring to Zoroastrians, the text uses specific words which are attested in primary sources and are well known among scholars and practitioners; they cannot be considered as fictive.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naorji. *Jarhoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī* ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sām̄j Vartamān, 1911.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Notes: Even if details on the maintenance of fire temples are not included in the text, there is an explanation of the subtle energies which emerge from the fire which is situated in fire temples, highlighting the importance of such spaces in the Zoroastrian religion and Ilm-e-Khshnoom.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naorji. *Jarhoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī* ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sām̄j Vartamān, 1911.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: Ilm-e-Khshnoom Institute

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naorji. *Jarhoštī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kṣnumnī Cāvī* ('the Key of Ilme Kṣnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sām̄j Vartamān, 1911.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: No, the author is also the leader of the society.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kṣnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: No

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Notes: In Ilm-e-Khshnoom as well as in other interpretations of Zoroastrianism, priestly education is accessible only to men.

Reference: Hinnells, John R.. *The Zoroastrian Diaspora. Religion and Migration*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2005.

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The author mentions his teachers who are believed to be semi-divine entities living in seclusion in Iran. In the foreword, the author praises and thanks them for the teachings received.

Reference: Errichiello, Mariano. "Ilme Kshnum: An Esoteric Interpretation of Zoroastrianism. History and Beliefs". Unpublished PhD Thesis, 2022.

Reference: Shroff, Behramshah Naoroji. *Jarhoṣṭī Dharm Samajavā Māṭe Ilme Kshnumnī Cāvī* ('the Key of Ilme Kshnum to Understand the Zoroastrian Religion'). Surat (Gujarat): Sām̄j Vartamān, 1911.

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

